

Evaluation of Contribution of Field, Resonance and Steric Effects of the Substituents in Pyridine Nucleus

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It has been concluded from an analysis of the pK_a values of a number of substituted pyridines that pyridine basicity depends on both inductive and resonance effects of the substituents. The per cent composition of inductive, resonance and steric effect of the substituents has been evaluated. The steric effect is found to play an insignificant role.

THE basic and nucleophilic properties of pyridine nitrogen are highly responsive to substituent effects and therefore have been used as sensitive probes in Brönsted and Hammett correlations. From a consideration of protonation equilibria and rates of quaternisation of substituted pyridines, it has been observed that ω -groups¹ exert inductive effect only². Contrary to the observation of Johnson *et al*³ and in accordance with the observations of Ehrenson, Brownlee and Taft³ the LD equation [extended Hammett equation (1)] is found to be more effective in describing substituent effects on pyridine nitrogen reactivity than the Hammett equation⁴.

$$Q_{\alpha} = L\sigma^-_{IX} + D\sigma^-_{RX} + h \quad \dots (1)$$

This conclusion has been based on the correlation obtained with both equations (Hammett and LD equations) for 4-substituted pyridine acidity data and quaternisation reactions⁴.

Swain and Lupton⁵, by making less assumptions than the earlier workers^{6,7}, proposed the position independent 'F' (field) and 'R' (resonance) parameters. Williams and Norrington⁸ evaluated in their work, the positional weighting factors f_j and r_j to explain the influence of F and R respectively at different positions, j. Therefore, they have proposed an equation [equation (2)] where α_i and β_i repre-

$$Q_{ijk} = Q_i^0 + \alpha_i f_j F_k + \beta_i r_j R_k \quad \dots (2)$$

sent the sensitivity of the reaction to the $f_j F_k$ and $r_j R_k$ describing field and resonance effects, respectively.

4-Substituted pyridines only have been considered in the earlier studies^{9,5}, but to make the study more general, we have considered substituents at different positions in pyridine. The regression analysis of thirtyfive pK_a data¹¹ gives equation (3) in accordance with Williams-Norrington equation (2).

$$pK_a = 5.14 - 3.70 (\pm 0.71) f_j F_k - 1.46 (\pm 1.1) r_j R_k \quad \dots (3)$$

$$n=35 \quad r=0.79 \quad s=1.50 \quad F=26.9$$

The percentage composition⁹ of inductive effect (P_F) and resonance effect (P_R) in the pK_a values are cal-

culated by the equations

$$P_F = (|\alpha_i| \times 100) / (|\alpha_i| + |\beta_i|)$$

$$\text{and } P_R = (|\beta_i| \times 100) / (|\alpha_i| + |\beta_i|)$$

and found to be 71.7 and 29.3%, respectively for pyridines. This suggests that the resonance effect of the substituents has a significant contribution in the pK_a of pyridines. To find out the contribution of steric effect for substituents at position 2 in pyridine, a steric parameter¹⁰, SD, is incorporated in WN-equation and the corresponding regression equation (4) is obtained where the values of α_i , β_i ,

$$Q_{ijk} = Q_i^0 + \alpha_i f_j F_k + \beta_i r_j R_k + \delta(SD)_k \quad \dots (4)$$

and δ are $-3.42 (\pm 0.72)$, $-1.74 (\pm 1.11)$ and $0.21 (\pm 0.24)$, respectively. The percentage composition of inductive, resonance and steric effects in the pK_a of pyridines is found to be 63.8, 32.4 and 3.8%, respectively. This shows that the steric effect plays an insignificant role in pyridine basicity.

By considering substituted quinolines and isoquinolines as pyridine derivatives (having substituents in pyridine ring only), their basicity data¹¹ are analysed using the equation (2). The corresponding regression equations for quinolines and isoquinolines are equations (5) and (6), respectively.

$$(pK_a)_Q = 5.69 - 3.98 (\pm 0.76) f_j F_k - 2.99 (\pm 0.74) r_j R_k \quad \dots (5)$$

$$n=15 \quad r=0.91 \quad s=0.94 \quad F=28.6$$

$$(pK_a)_{iSOQ} = 5.73 - 4.11 (\pm 0.91) f_j F_k - 2.51 (\pm 1.13) r_j R_k \quad \dots (6)$$

$$n=9 \quad r=0.94 \quad s=0.804 \quad F=26.1$$

The percentage compositions of the $L_a D_a$ parameters have been calculated similarly and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PERCENT COMPOSITION OF INDUCTIVE, RESONANCE AND STERIC EFFECTS ON THE BASICITY OF QUINOLINES AND ISOQUINOLINES

Equations	P_F	P_R	P_S
5	57.2	42.8	—
6	62.1	37.9	—
7	53.4	40.4	6.2
8	62.5	32.9	4.6

Hoping that substituents either at position 2 or at positions 1 and 3 exert steric influence on the basicity of quinolines and isoquinolines respectively, the pK_a values have been correlated with equation (4) and the regression equations (7) and (8) are derived.

$$(pK_a)_Q = 5.894 - 4.1 (\pm 0.743) f_j F_k - 3.094 (\pm 0.719) r_j R_k - 0.477 (\pm 0.374) (SD) \quad \dots (7)$$

$$n=15 \quad r=0.92 \quad s=0.918 \quad F=20.6$$

$$(pK_a)_{isoQ} = 6.137 - 4.384 (\pm 0.923) f_j F_k - 2.314 (\pm 1.148) r_j R_k - 0.316 (\pm 0.353) (SD) \quad \dots (8)$$

$$n=9 \quad r=0.95 \quad s=0.815 \quad F=17.17$$

The percentage composition values of individual parameters have been calculated and given in Table 1. It is observed that steric effect plays an insignificant role to explain the basicity of the nitrogen atom of both quinolines and isoquinolines also.

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